

The Digital Democracy Score (DDS): A Prototype Tool for Measuring Digital Democracy

WP2 – Task 2.9

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Document Information

This methodology paper outlines the Digital Democracy Score’s methodology. The tool is a prototype that is available and can be used at <https://www.digital-democracy.net>. It was developed as part of the EU research project INNOVADE: INNOVative DEMocracy through digitalisation (<https://innovade-democracy.eu/>).

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The Digital Democracy Score (DDS)

<https://www.digital-democracy.net>: A Prototype Tool for Measuring Varieties of Digital Democracy

The Digital Democracy Score (<https://www.digital-democracy.net>) is a prototype tool for measuring how well digital democracy projects or technologies (apps, websites, software, platforms, etc) realise various dimensions of digital democracy. It asks a series of survey-like questions, based on which it calculates a variety of digital democracy scores that are all combined into one overall Digital Democracy Score (DDS). The other scores, on which the DDS is based, are: Constitutional Digital Democracy Score (CODDI), Deliberative Digital Democracy Score (DIDDI), Participatory Digital Democracy Score (PADDI), Representative Digital Democracy Score (REDDI), and Pluralist Digital Democracy Score (PLUDDI). The scores use a rating scale from 0 to 100 where 0 indicates a very low level and 100 a very high level.

After asking a variety of questions, the tool presents the calculation results and further information on digital democracy.

Please note that the tool is not fully developed but a prototype. Therefore, it does not claim to have the ultimate methodology, but only presents one of many methodologies, is web-based only, and only available in English.

1. Measuring Democracy

Well-known indicators for measuring democracy include Freedom House's Freedom in the World (FIW), Polity5 (P5), V-Dem: Varieties of Democracy, and the Economist Intelligence Unit Democracy Index (DI). Table 1 gives an overview of some features of these indicators. Here are some observations on these general indicators of democracy:

- **Expert surveys:**
The major democracy indicators are expert surveys conducted at the level of nation-states.
- **Methodological nationalism:**
They do not focus on subnational levels such as the city, the municipality, the council, or the federal state. They also do not focus on the transnational level.
- **Non-scalability:**
They are not scalable.
- **Restricted models of democracy:**
Except for V-Dem, they have a focus on one or two models of democracy, especially representative democracy with a focus on elections and elected governments, as well as constitutional democracy. Other levels of democracy are missing or are underrepresented.
- **Restricted understanding of democracy:**
Participation is often defined and understood as participation in elections. For example, Freedom House's (2025) dimension of political pluralism and participation asks survey questions that understand participation primarily as "electoral opportunities". In Polity V's methodology, participation is understood as the "competitiveness of participation"

(Marshall and Gurr 2020, 26), which is defined as political conditions where “political groups [...] regularly compete for political influence at the national level; ruling groups and coalitions regularly, voluntarily transfer central power to competing groups” (Marshall and Gurr 2020, 27). In such measurements of participation, participation is primarily understood as the participation of citizens and parties in elections.

- **Lack of focus on digital democracy:**

Aspects of digital democracy hardly play a role in general democracy indicators.

In contrast to some of these methodologies, the Digital Democracy Score (DDS) takes an approach that is not focused on a single model of democracy. It does not privilege a particular model. Inspired by the Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) approach, it utilises a variety of models of (digital) democracy: constitutional digital democracy, deliberative digital democracy, participatory digital democracy, representative digital democracy, direct digital democracy, and pluralist digital democracy.

DDS is not purely focused on the nation-state. Its main focus is on digital democracy projects. Operators of such projects are asked to provide information on their projects by answering survey questions, based on which a variety of Digital Democracy Scores are calculated that are then combined into an overall Digital Democracy Score. The methodology is scalable; it can be applied at the local, municipal level, but also at the regional, national, or transnational level, that is, at all organisational levels of digital democracy.

	FIW	P5	V-Dem	DI
Scope	Nation-states	Nation-states	Nation-states	Nation-states
Method	Expert assessment of 208 countries (2025)	Expert assessment of 163 countries for the period from 1800 to 2018	Expert survey	Assessment of 202 countries (2024) for varying time periods ranging from 1789 at the earliest to 2024
Frequency of data updates	Annually	Irregular updates of the methodology and data	Annually	Annually
Respondents	136 analysts and 45 advisers (2025)	Country experts	More than 4,000 country experts (2025), usually at least 5 experts per country	Analysts, number unknown
Indicator(s)	Freedom in the World Indicator	Democracy Score 0-10, Autocracy Score 0-10, Polity Score = Democracy Score – Autocracy Score	Five core indicators derived from various variables: Electoral Democracy Index (EDI), Liberal Democracy Index (LDI), Participatory Democracy Index (PDI), Deliberative Democracy Index, Egalitarian Democracy Index	Democracy Index
Indicator range	0-100	-10 to +10	Interval from 0-1 (three positions after the decimal point => can be recoded into scores from 0-1000)	0-10
Number of questions or variables	25 (10 questions on political rights, 15 on civil liberties)	9 (4 variables on democracy, 5 on autocracy)	V-Dem Full+Others 2025: 531 variables, 245 indices	Average score of five sub-indicators (electoral process and pluralism, functioning of government, political participation, political culture, civil liberties); the sub-indicators are derived from a set of 60 dichotomous variables
Aspects of democracy	Electoral democracy, civil liberties: model of representative and constitutional democracy	Type of political system with a focus on electoral democracy: model of representative democracy	Varieties of models of democracy: representative democracy, direct democracy, constitutional democracy, participatory democracy, deliberative democracy	Electoral democracy, civil liberties: models of representative and constitutional democracy
Data source	Freedom House (2025)	Marshall and Gurr (2020)	V-Dem Institute (2025)	Economist Intelligence Unit (2024)

Table 1: A classification of methodologies for measuring democracy

2. Measuring Digital Democracy

Just like there are general democracy indicators, there are also indicators for measuring digital democracy. They include, for example, the UN E-Participation Index (EPI), Freedom House's Freedom on the Net (FOTN), V-Dem's Digital Society Project indicators (DSP), and the DigiPart (Digital Participation)-Index (DPI). Table 2 gives an overview of the core features of these digital democracy indicators.

Some observations on these indicators of digital democracy:

- **Methodological nationalism:**

Except for DPI, they all operate at the level of nation-states. Just like measuring democracy, measuring digital democracy has a methodological nationalist bias.

- **Expert surveys:**

In the utilised methods, there is a focus on experts and researchers classifying digital democracy. No or only little input is sought from those who operate digital democracy projects.

- **Restricted models of democracy:**

In terms of models of democracy, there is a strong focus on representative and constitutional digital democracy.

	EPI	FOTN	DSP	DPI
Scope	Nation-states	Nation-states	Nation-states	Federal states/cantons
Method	Classification of answers to a member state survey	Survey focused on 72 countries (2024)	Survey focused on 179 countries (2025)	Assessment of the level of participation in three domains of digital politics: opinion-formation, co-creation, and decision-making
Frequency of data updates	Bi-annual	Annual	Annual	Irregular
Respondents	UN member states	At least one expert researcher or organisation per country	Usually, at least 5 experts per country	Researcher-coded assessments
Indicators	UN E-Participation Index	Freedom on the Net	35 stand-alone indicators based on 35 survey questions	DigiPart-Index
Indicator range	0-1: 0-0.25 low, 0.25-0.50 medium, 0.50-0.75 high, 0.75-1.00 very high	0-100: 0-39 not free, 40-69: partly free, 70-100: free	Ranges vary	0-100
Number of questions or variables	Composite indicator calculated based on the assessment of answers to specific questions in the UN E-Government Survey. These questions are focused on the topics of e-information, e-consultation, and e-decision-making, with a focus on what e-services are provided by the government	Composite indicator taking three dimensions into account: a) obstacles to access (economic or political control of infrastructures, ISPs and regulatory bodies; b) limits on content (censorship, blocking); c) violations of user rights (freedom of online expression, surveillance and privacy, cyberattacks, online harassment; a) max. 25 points allocated by 5 survey questions, b) max. 35 points allocated by 8 survey questions, c) max. 40 points allocated by eight questions	35 survey questions on five overall topic areas: false information, online freedom of expression, government regulation, online media polarisation, online harassment and hate speech	A total of seven technologies is classified on a scale from 1 (low participation) to 5 (high participation): 3 opinion-formation technologies (e-deliberation, e-civic education, e-transparency), 2 co-creation technologies (e-consultation, e-demand), 2 decision-making technologies (e-ID, e-voting)
Aspects of democracy	Representative digital democracy	Constitutional digital democracy	Constitutional digital democracy, pluralist digital democracy	Representative digital democracy, deliberative digital democracy, participatory digital democracy
Data source	United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2020, 2022, 2024a, 2024b)	Freedom House (2024)	Digital Society Project (2025)	Serdült, Hofmann, and Vayenas (2022) and Hofmann et al. (2023)

Table 2: A classification of methodologies for measuring digital democracy

3. The Digital Democracy Score

The Digital Democracy Score (DDS) takes an approach that differs from the methods of measuring digital democracy discussed in section 2. It has the following main features:

- **Project-focused methodology beyond methodological nationalism:**
The DDS uses a survey methodology that seeks inputs from the operators of digital democracy projects.
- **Scalable methodology:**
The DDS is scalable. Its methodology can be applied to projects operated at various organisational levels, including municipalities/local cities, the region, the nation-state, and transnationalism.
- **Varieties of digital democracy:**
The DDS does not privilege a single model of democracy and digital democracy. It utilises a variety of models of digital democracy, namely constitutional, deliberative, participatory, representative, direct and pluralist digital democracy.
- **Varieties of digital democracy scores:**
Based on which forms of digital democracy a particular technology or project utilises, the DDS provides a variety of scoring mechanisms appropriate for assessing different forms and technologies of digital democracy (such as e-voting, political discussion forums, participatory budgeting, etc).
- **Unity of digital democracy's variety:**
The DDS's methodology unites a variety of digital democracy scores that it first calculates into one overall score between 0 (very low) and 100 (very high).

The DDS methodology calculates a composite score and various indexes based on questions asked in a survey (see the survey questionnaire in this document's Appendix). The platform calculates the Digital Democracy Score (DDS) and several sub-scores, the digital democracy indexes (if applicable):

CODDI: Constitutional Digital Democracy Index

DEDDI: Deliberative Digital Democracy Index

PADDI: Participatory Digital Democracy Index

REDDI: Representative Digital Democracy Index

DIDDI: Direct Digital Democracy Index

PLUDDI: Pluralist Digital Democracy Index

Each index is calculated based on the answers to several questions. The values of these questions are used for calculating the respective index.

The overall Digital Democracy Score (DDS) is a composite index that adds up the six indexes as weighted summands. CODDI always has a weight of 0.4 (40%) because it is particularly important. Aspects of constitutional democracy, such as freedom of speech, right to human dignity, right to life and physical integrity, etc., are important in all democracies.

The survey's introductory part asks questions about the importance of the models of democracy that the indexes represent. The answers to these questions determine the weights. REDDI, DIDDI, DEDDI, PADDI, and PLUDDI together have a weight of 0.6 (60%) in the DDS.

For each index, except CODDI, there is an introductory question for determining the respective weight. If the answer is "There is no such feature", then the respective index weight is zero, and no questions are asked about this feature. In the case of pluralist democracy (PLUDDI), the weight cannot be zero, so the respective questions are always asked. Features that are manifestations of representative democracy, direct democracy, deliberative democracy, and participatory democracy are not necessarily present in each digital democracy project/app/platform. Therefore, questions are only asked if the user indicates that such a feature is used in the analysed technology or project.

One note on REDDI and DIDDI: The calculation of DIDDI includes all questions asked for REDDI. This means that these questions are only asked once, but the values are included for the calculation of DIDDI too. In case that REDDI is not applicable, but DIDDI then all REDDI questions need to be asked for inclusion into the calculation of DIDDI. REDDI has a weight of 0.35 (35%) of DIDDI and is rounded for inclusion in DIDDI ($0.35 \times \text{REDDI}$).

The sequence of questions in the survey is: introductory questions (weighting), CODDI questions, DEDDI, PADDI, REDDI, DIDDI, PLUDDI.

The applicable index scores as well as the DDS are shown on the final screen. Recommendations are provided on how to improve the scores that are below 60.

DDS Rating Scale:

All indexes and scores take on integer values between 0 and 100 points

> 90: very high level

81-90: good level

61-80: medium level

51-60: low level

< 50: very low level

Calculation Method of the Digital Democracy Score (DDS)

$\text{DDS} = 0,40 \times \text{CODDI} + \text{deddi_weight} \times \text{DEDDI} + \text{paddi_weight} \times \text{PADDI} + \text{reddi_weight} \times \text{REDDI} + \text{diddi_weight} \times \text{DIDDI} + \text{pluddi_weight} \times \text{PLUDDI}$ [rounded to a full number]

$\text{deddi_weight} + \text{paddi_weight} + \text{reddi_weight} + \text{diddi_weight} + \text{pluddi_weight} = 0.60$

The survey's introductory questions ask for each model of digital democracy (except constitutional digital democracy), how important it is in the analysed project/technology/app. It can take on a score between 0 and 3, 0 means that the model is not used at all, 1 means the model is used but plays a minor role, 2 means the model is important, and 3 means that the model is very important.

An example question is i_q1 (defines deddi_weight: weight of deliberative digital democracy; see also the DDS questionnaire in the appendix):

i_q1 How central to your project, app, or platform are online debates?

Online debating is a very important feature [value=3]

It is one of the important features [value=2]

It exists but is not part of the most important features [value=1]

There is no such feature [value=0]

The weights are calculated in the following way:

deddi: importance of deliberative digital democracy in the analysed project/tool [value 0-3]

paddi: importance of participatory digital democracy in the analysed project/tool [value 0-3]

reddi: importance of representative digital democracy in the analysed project/tool [value 0-3]

diddi: importance of direct digital democracy in the analysed project/tool [value 0-3]

pluddi: importance of pluralist digital democracy in the analysed project/tool [value 1-3]

pluddi_weight (weight of pluralist digital democracy) takes on a value between 1 and 3 because questions of pluralism are always present in democracies.

$$\text{deddi_weight} = \text{deddi} / (\text{deddi} + \text{paddi} + \text{reddi} + \text{diddi} + \text{pluddi}) \times 0.6$$

$$\text{paddi_weight} = \text{paddi} / (\text{deddi} + \text{paddi} + \text{reddi} + \text{diddi} + \text{pluddi}) \times 0.6$$

$$\text{reddi_weight} = \text{reddi} / (\text{deddi} + \text{paddi} + \text{reddi} + \text{diddi} + \text{pluddi}) \times 0.6$$

$$\text{diddi_weight} = \text{diddi} / (\text{deddi} + \text{paddi} + \text{reddi} + \text{diddi} + \text{pluddi}) \times 0.6$$

$$\text{pluddi_weight} = \text{pluddi} / (\text{deddi} + \text{paddi} + \text{reddi} + \text{diddi} + \text{pluddi}) \times 0.6$$

An example calculation: Let us assume that the introductory questions determine the following importance scores:

deddi = 3 (very important), paddi = 3 (very important), reddi = 1 (minor importance), diddi = 0 (not used), pluddi = 2 (important)

coddi_weight = 0.4 (pre-defined)

$$\text{deddi_weight} = 3 / (3 + 3 + 1 + 0 + 2) \times 0.6 = 3 / 9 \times 0.6 = 0.2 \text{ (20\%)}$$

$$\text{paddi_weight} = 3 / 9 \times 0.6 = 0.2 \text{ (20\%)}$$

$$\text{reddi_weight} = 1 / 9 \times 0.6 = 0.0667 \text{ (6.67\%)}$$

$$\text{diddi_weight} = 0 / 9 \times 0.6 = 0 \text{ (0\%)}$$

$$\text{pluddi_weight} = 2 / 9 \times 0.6 = 0.1333 \text{ (13.3\%)}$$

Let us assume the survey tool calculates the following digital democracy indexes:

CODDI = 95 (very high)

DEDDI = 85 (good)

PADDI = 85 (good)

REDDI = 75 (medium)

DIDDI: not calculated, not applicable

PLUDDI = 55 (low)

The Digital Democracy Score (DDS) is calculated in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DDS} &= 95 \times 0.4 + 85 \times 0.2 + 85 \times 0.2 + 75 \times 0.0667 + 0 + 55 \times 0.1333 = \\ &= 38.00 + 17.00 + 17.00 + 5.00 + 0 + 7.33 = 84.33 \approx \underline{84} \end{aligned}$$

DDS Rating Scale:

> 90: very high level

81-90: good level

61-80: medium level

51-60: low level

< 50: very low level

=> 84 means DDS has a good level.

Let us assume all indexes have the highest value of 100, then the DDS also takes on a level of 100:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DDS} &= 100 \times 0.4 + 100 \times 0.2 + 100 \times 0.2 + 100 \times 0.0667 + 0 + 100 \times 0.1333 \times 100 = \\ &= 40 + 20 + 20 + 6.7 + 0 + 13.3 = 100 \end{aligned}$$

Calculation Methods of the Digital Democracy Indexes

Based on the survey questions (see the Annex for the full questionnaire), the digital democracy indexes are calculated in the following ways.

The survey questions have variable names that use the syntax si_{qj} where i stands for the survey's section number and j for the question number within that section.

The survey sections (i) are organised in the following way:

Section 1: Constitutional Digital Democracy Index (CODDI)

Section 2: Deliberative Digital Democracy Index (DEDDI)

Section 3: Participatory Digital Democracy Index (PADDI)

Section 4: Representative Digital Democracy Index (REDDI)

Section 5: Direct Digital Democracy Index (DIDDI)

Section 6: Pluralist Digital Democracy Index (PLUDDI)

There are the following number of questions in the respective sections (j):

Section 1: 26

Section 2: 24

Section 3: 21

Section 4: 17

Section 5: 6

Section 6: 7

There are N=101 survey questions. Only those survey questions are asked that belong to digital democracy models that apply to the analysed tool/project. Which questions are asked is determined by the introductory section's five questions. They help define the indexes' weights used in the calculation of the Digital Democracy Score (DDS). So overall, there are 106 survey questions, 5 determining the digital democracy indexes' weights and 101 questions helping to calculate the six digital democracy indexes.

Calculation of the Constitutional Digital Democracy Index (CODDI)

The survey's CODDI section consists of 26 questions.

$$\text{CODDI} = 2 \times \sum_{i=1}^{26} s1_{qi}$$

The maximum of the sum of all 26 CODDI questions' values is 50. CODDI is calculated by doubling this sum so that it takes on a value between 0 and 100.

Calculation of the Deliberative Digital Democracy Index (DEDDI)

The survey's DEDDI section consists of 24 questions.

DEDDI is calculated as the sum of the value of eleven DEDDI dimensions. Each dimension's value is calculated based on one or more questions.

$$\text{DEDDI} = D1 + D2 + D3 + D4 + D5 + D6 + D7 + D8 + D9 + D10 + D11$$

$$D1 = s2_{q1} + s2_{q2} \times 2 + s2_{q3} \times 2 + s2_{q4}$$

$$D2 = \text{ROUND}(s2_{q5} * (5/3))$$

s2_q5 takes on a value between 0-3, it is weighted so that D2 takes on a value between 0-5

$$D3 = 2 \times s2_{q6} + 8 \times s2_{q7}$$

$$D4 = s2_{q12} + s2_{q8} \times (s2_{q8} + s2_{q9} + s2_{q10} + s2_{q11} + s2_{q13} + s2_{q14})$$

s2_q8 asks if the used discussion forums are moderated or not. If not, then D4 takes on a maximum of 1 point, as s2_q8 is then set to a value of 0

$$D5 = \text{ROUND} ((s2_q15 + s2_q16 + s2_q17) \times 10/3)$$

D5 is rounded so that it is a whole number

$$D6 = 3 \times s2_q18 + 2 \times s2_q19$$

$$D7 = s2_q20 \times 5$$

$$D8 = \text{ROUND} (s2_q21 \times 10/3)$$

D8 is rounded so that it is a whole number

$$D9 = \text{ROUND} (s2_q22 \times 10/3)$$

D9 is rounded so that it is a whole number

$$D10 = \text{ROUND} (s2_q23 \times 10/3)$$

D10 is rounded so that it is a whole number

$$D11 = \text{ROUND} (s2_q24 \times 5/3)$$

D11 is rounded so that it is a whole number

The following list shows the maximum value of each dimension:

D1 Access and inclusion: 10

D2 Anonymity: 5

D3 Guidelines: 10

D4 Moderation: 10

D5 Colonisation: 10

D6 Discursive equality: 10

D7 Quality of discussion: 10

D8 Truth: 10

D9 Incivility: 10

D10 Threats of violence: 10

D11 Impact on society: 5

Calculation of the Participatory Digital Democracy Index (PADDI)

The survey's PADDI section consists of 21 questions.

$$\text{PADDI} = \sum_{i=1}^{21} s3_qi$$

Calculation of the Representative Digital Democracy Index (REDDI)

The survey's REDDI section consists of 17 questions.

$$\text{REDDI} = \sum_{i=1}^{17} s4_{qi}$$

Calculation of the Direct Digital Democracy Index (DIDDI)

The survey's DIDDI section consists of 6 questions.

$$\text{DIDDI} = s5_{q1} + s5_{q2} + s5_{q3} + s5_{q4} + s5_{q5} + s5_{q6} + \text{ROUND}(0,35 \times \text{REDDI})$$

Direct democracy always includes features of electoral democracy that are measured by REDDI. Therefore, DIDDI needs to incorporate the result of REDDI. Methodologically, this is achieved by first calculating REDDI and then adding it as a summand with a weight of 35% to DIDDI.

Calculation of the Pluralist Digital Democracy Index (PLUDDI)

The survey's PLUDDI section consists of 7 questions.

$$\text{PLUDDI} = 5 \times \sum_{i=1}^7 s6_{qi}$$

The maximum of the sum of all seven PLUDDI questions' values is 20. PLUDDI is calculated by multiplying this sum by 5 so that it takes on a value between 0 and 100.

Presentation of the DDS's Calculation Results

After asking a variety of questions, the DDS tool calculates the respective digital democracy scores and outputs them in the form of a text as well as a spider chart. The next two figures give an idea of how this looks like. In addition, recommendations on how to improve features of digital democracy can be downloaded. The tool's prototype can be tested at <https://www.digital-democracy-net>.

DIGITAL DEMOCRACY SCORE (DDS) RESULTS

0..100 points

> 90: very high level

81-90: good level

61-80: medium level

51-60: low level

< 50: very low level

Constitutional Digital Democracy Index (CODDI): 100

CODDI measures how well your digital democracy app/system respects democratic constitutional rights (basic and human rights)

Deliberative Digital Democracy Index (DEDDI): 100

DEDDI measures the quality of online debating your digital democracy app/system supports.

Participatory Digital Democracy Index (PADDI): 94

PADDI measures the quality of political participation your digital democracy app/system supports.

Figure 1: An example output of the DDS' calculation results

SPIDER CHART OF YOUR DIGITAL DEMOCRACY SCORES:

You can download the chart as an image file by right-clicking on the image and saving it.

Figure 2: An example spider chart that visualises the DDS's calculation results

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Appendix: The Digital Democracy Score (DDS) Survey Questionnaire

The answers to a question result in a numeric value that is assigned to the question's variable. In the questionnaire that follows, the coded values, which is an integer number, are provided after or below the answer options.

Introductory Questions

Digital democracy is the use of digital media in the practice of democracy. It refers to the mediation, support, and enablement of democracy by digital technologies. This tool helps you measure the qualities of concrete digital democracy applications or projects. It calculates a variety of digital democracy scores and combines them into one overall Digital Democracy Score (DDS), depending on what features your application or project uses. The tool will ask you a set of questions that will be used for this purpose. No personal data is stored. At the end, it will calculate the DDS and show the result.

Let us start with basic questions about the features of your app or project. This will help me determine what questions I will ask and use.

Digital democracy tools and projects can have different features. Can you please indicate which of the following features the tool or project you want to test supports. Multiple answers are possible. Depending on your answers, there will be specific questions and we will skip questions on those features that your tool or project does not support.

By "e-voting" we do not mean liking a social media post or voting something up or down on rating platforms such as Reddit. Rather, "e-voting" refers to the use of electronic voting systems in local, regional, national, or international elections.

Please note that by "e-participation" and "citizen participation tools" we do not mean the participation in online elections, the participation in online discussion, or the reading of online information. Rather, "e-participation" is about more active forms of engagement such as users' and citizens' reporting of faults or errors (e.g. FixMyStreet), structured online feedback on proposals, the online co-production of new ideas (idea-generation), the online co-creation of suggestions, recommendations, policies, campaigns, or decisions. Examples of such e-participation are digital participatory budgeting platforms (e.g. Decidim, Consul), crowdsourcing platforms for policy ideas (e.g. pol.is), civic tech co-creation platforms (e.g. Your Priorities, vTaiwan, Loomio), online petition systems, cyberprotest and online civic campaigns (e.g. change.org), collaborative law portals (e.g. EU – "Have Your Say"), wikis used for political purposes (e.g. political entries on Wikipedia), etc.

i_q0 Digital democracy features

Which of the following features does your digital democracy tool or project support?

Online debating and discussion

- Citizen participation tools (e-participation)
- e-voting in local, regional, national, or international elections
- e-voting of citizens on particular topics in referenda on the local, regional, national, or international level

DEDDI (Deliberative Digital Democracy Index) Weight

i_q1 How central to your project, app, or platform are online debates?

- Online debating is a very important feature. 3
- It is one of the important features. 2
- It exists but is not part of the most important features. 1
- There is no such feature. 0

PADDI (Participatory Digital Democracy Index) Weight

i_q2 How central to your project, app, or platform are citizen participation tools?

- Citizen participation is a very important feature. 3
- It is one of the important features. 2
- It exists but is not part of the most important features. 1
- There is no such feature. 0

REDDI (Representative Digital Democracy Index) Weight

i_q3 How central to your project, app, or platform is online voting in electing political representatives?

- It is a very important feature. 3
- It is one of the important features. 2
- It exists but is not part of the most important features. 1
- There is no such feature. 0

DIDDI (Direct Digital Democracy Index) Weight

i_q4 How central to your project, app, or platform is online voting in referenda-like elections to let citizens decide on particular topics?

- It is a very important feature. 3
- It is one of the important features. 2
- It exists but is not part of the most important features. 1
- There is no such feature. 0

PLUDDI (Pluralist Digital Democracy Index) Weight

i_q5 What is the platform's general approach to decision-making when differing views emerge among participants or when e-votes are undertaken that require clear decisions?

- Decisions are made based on the majority view or the most popular option. 1
- The majority view is important, but efforts are made to integrate minority perspectives where possible. 2

- The platform prioritises finding consensus between all participants before final decisions are made. 3
- There is no specific approach. It depends on the process or issue, and there are different design options that can be chosen. 1

1: Constitutional Digital Democracy

Part 1.1: Human Dignity and the Right to Life

s1_q1

Does the platform have a policy that explicitly prohibits hate speech (e.g. racism, xenophobia, antisemitism, homophobia, etc.) and defines actions that are taken in the case of hate speech?

- Yes 3
- No 0

s1_q2

Apart from the terms users agree to at sign-up, are the platform's policies communicated in other ways?

Examples are: summaries or reminders that are sent out to the registered users, posting tutorials, introductory videos, etc,

- Yes 3
- No 0

s1_q3

Does the platform/system/app have a policy that makes clear what happens if users voice threats of violence or harass other users?

- Yes 3
- No 0

s1_q4

Is it possible for users on the platform/system/app to post information (for example, by making comments, uploading information or content, discussing with others, making proposals/suggestions, etc.)?

- Yes
- No

IF NO => GO TO QUESTION s1_q7

IF YES => CONTINUE with s1_q5 and s1_q6

s1_q5

To what degree is the posting of content on your platform moderated?

- There is no moderation 0
- There are algorithms identifying suspicious content 1
- There are human moderators identifying suspicious content 2

The are algorithms and human moderators identifying suspicious content 3

s1_q6

Let us assume that there is a user who voices threats to kill a particular citizen with whom they disagree politically on the platform/system/app (e.g. in a public comment, discussion, posting, proposal, suggestion, draft, direct message, etc). What happens in such a case?

Nothing 0

The user is warned not to do such things 1

The user is banned 1

The content is removed and the user is neither warned nor banned 1

The content is removed and the user is warned 2

The content is removed and the user is banned 2

The content is removed and the incident is reported to the police 3

Part 1.2: Inclusion

s1_q7

Who can access and use the platform/system?

Everyone or everyone living in the community who is older than a defined age. 2

Not everyone. Certain groups in the community are not allowed to participate. 0

s1_q8

There are groups in society that are less likely to use online politics platforms, especially those with lower income and education, elderly people, people in rural areas, or refugees. Have measures been undertaken to especially appeal to such groups and try to make them participate?

Yes. 2

Not yet, but we plan to do so in the future. 0

No. 0

s1_q9

There are citizens who do not have access to the Internet. Have measures been undertaken to try to foster the participation of such citizens?

No. 0

Not yet, but we plan to do so in the future. 0

Yes. 1

s1_q10

If yes, what measures have been undertaken? (multiple answers)

Support staff or training for the use of the platform is offered. 0,25

We held events targeted at non-Internet users that tried to engage them. 0,25

It is possible to participate in offline versions for undertaking the actions that the digital technology supports. 0,5

s1_q11

Have measures been implemented that support people with disabilities in using the platform/system?

- Yes. 2
- Not yet, but we plan to do so in the future. 0
- No. 0

s1_q12

How many languages does the platform/system support?

- One, the dominant language spoken in the community. 0
- Two, the dominant language spoken in the community and another language (not English). 1
- Two, the dominant language spoken in the community and English. 1
- More than two, but not English. 1
- More than two, including English. 2

Part 1.3: Freedom of Assembly, Association, Expression, and Information

s1_q13

In terms of political and civil society groups active in society, what groups are, if applicable, able to participate on the platform (by, for example, posting information, engaging in discussions and other activities)?

- Only the government. 0
- The governing and other elected parties. 0
- All political parties, but no civil society organisations. 0
- All political parties that respect human rights, democracy, and the constitution, but no civil society organisations. 0
- All civil society groups, but no political parties. 0
- All civil society groups that respect human rights, democracy, and the constitution, but no political parties. 0
- All political parties and all civil society organisations. 1
- All political parties and all civil society organisations that respect human rights, democracy, and the constitution. 2

s1_q14

Is criticism of the government in the information, content, and discussions on the platform allowed or censored in any way?

- Criticism of the government is allowed. 1
- Criticism of the government is censored. 0

s1_q15

Is criticism of non-governmental forces (NGOs, religious or philosophical groups, single individuals, economic interest groups, etc.) in the information, content, and discussions on the platform allowed or censored in any way?

- Criticism of non-governmental forces is allowed. 1
- Criticism of non-governmental forces is censored. 0

s1_q16

What happens if so-called fake news or misinformation, news or information that does not correspond to facts and tries to mislead the public on important topics, is present on the platform?

- Nothing, there is no action on the side of the platform. 0
- The information is not removed, and the user is warned. 0
- The information is not removed, and the user is blocked. 0
- The information is removed, and the user is not warned or blocked. 1
- The information is removed, and the user is warned or blocked. 1
- There is fact-checking so that fake news is highlighted as such, and a fact-check is published, and users are pointed towards it. 2

s1_q17

In the information, content, and discussions on the platform, how often can one hear demands that the fundamental rights of certain groups should be restricted?

- Never 2
- Occasionally 0
- Frequently 0
- Very frequently 0

s1_q18

IF previous question is not "Never":

Can you assess how many of 100 postings on average contain such demands to restrict the fundamental rights of certain groups?

- 1 1
- 2-5 0
- 6-10 0
- 11-15 0
- 16-20 0
- 21-30 0
- 31-40 0
- More than 40 0

s1_q19

[Based on VDEM, harassment of journalists (v2meharjrn)]

Are individual users harassed – i.e., threatened with libel, arrested, imprisoned, beaten, or killed – by governmental or powerful nongovernmental actors for democratic things they say there?

- Users would not dare to engage in activities that would offend powerful actors because harassment or worse would be certain to occur. 0
- Some users occasionally offend powerful actors, but they are almost always harassed or

worse and eventually are forced to stop. 0

Some users who offend powerful actors are forced to stop, but others manage to continue practising criticism freely for long periods of time. 0

It is rare for any users to be harassed for offending powerful actors, and if this were to happen, those responsible for the harassment would be identified and punished. 1

Users are never harassed by governmental or powerful nongovernmental actors while engaged in legitimate online activities. 2

s1_q20

[Based on VDEM media censorship effort (v2mecenefm)]

Does the government directly or indirectly attempt to censor democratically legitimate content on the platform?

Attempts to censor are direct and routine. 0

Attempts to censor are indirect but nevertheless routine. 0

Attempts to censor are direct but limited to especially sensitive issues. 0

Attempts to censor are indirect and limited to especially sensitive issues. 0

The government rarely attempts to censor the platform in any way, and when such exceptional attempts are discovered, the responsible officials are usually punished. 1

The government never attempts to censor the platform in any way. 2

s1_q21

[Based on V-DEM freedom of academic and cultural expression (v2clacfree)]

Is there freedom of democratic expression related to political issues on the platform?

Censorship and intimidation are frequent. Political expressions are severely restricted or controlled. 0

Weakly respected. Direct criticism of dominant forces is mostly met with repression. 0

Somewhat respected. Strong criticism of dominant forces is sometimes met with repression. 0

Mostly respected. There are a few limitations on freedom of expression, and resulting sanctions tend to be infrequent and soft. 0

Fully respected by public authorities. There are no restrictions on freedom of expression. 3

Part 1.4: Privacy, Data Protection, and Data Security

s1_q22

Does your platform have a privacy and data protection policy that clearly defines what, how and for what purposes it collects, stores, processes, and uses personal data?

Yes, we have such a policy. 2

No, not yet, but we plan to have such a policy in the future. 0

No, we do not have such a policy. 0

s1_q23

Does your platform ask for the users' informed consent for the collection, storage, processing, and usage of data about them?

Yes, we ask users for informed consent. 2

No, not yet, but we plan to in the future ask users for informed consent. 0

No, we do not ask users for informed consent. 0

s1_q24

Do you obtain and use data about users from sources external to your platform for purposes such as targeted advertising, personalisation, or other forms of monitoring or targeting?

No. 2

Yes, but we plan to reduce that amount of data. 0

Yes. 0

s1_q25

How do you assess the platform's security mechanisms against data breaches, hacking, identity theft, and data manipulation?

Excellent 2

Very good 1

Good 1

Medium 0

Poor 0

Not existent 0

s1_q26

How often have data breaches, successful hacking into the platform, or foreign interferences into or manipulation of data taken place?

Never 2

Once 1

2-5 times 0

5-10 times 0

More than 10 times 0

2: Deliberative Digital Democracy

This section of the survey is about the organisation of online debates. The tool will ask a series of questions about it.

Part 2.1: Access and inclusion (Rightness)

s2_q1

What share of individuals in your community has access to digital tools that allow them to access your digital democracy application?

If you have no data available, please make an informed estimation.

0-10%

- 0-10%
- 11-20%
- 21-30%
- 31-40%
- 41-50%
- 51-60%
- 61-70%
- 71-80%
- 81-90%
- 91-100%

Coding:

0-30: Low = 0

31-70: Medium = 1

71-100: High = 2

s2_q2

And what share of individuals in your community who have access to digital tools has used your digital tool?

If you have no data available, please make an informed estimation.

- 0-10%
- 11-20%
- 21-30%
- 31-40%
- 41-50%
- 51-60%
- 61-70%
- 71-80%
- 81-90%
- 91-100%

Coding:

0-30: Low = 0

31-70: Medium = 1

71-100: High = 2

s2_q3

Have measures been undertaken to promote the inclusion of individuals and groups who are unlikely to participate in online debates?

- No 0
- Yes: 1

s2_q4

If yes: How do you assess the intensity of such measures?

- There is a low level of such measures (infrequently): 0
- There is a medium level of such measures (sometimes): Medium: 1

There is a high level of such measures (regularly): Medium: 2

Part 2.2: Anonymity

s2_q5

Can you tell us how anonymous or non-anonymous debate in your online-forum is?

Users can post anonymously 0

Users have to register with an e-mail address 1

Users have to provide some form of personal identification such as a phone number or registration code sent to their home 2

Users have to register using an identity check system verifying IDs, passports, etc. 3

Part 2.3: Guidelines

s2_q6 Netiquette

Q6 Does your forum have guidelines and rules of what online behaviour is acceptable and unacceptable?

No 0

Yes 1

IF YES:

s2_q7

Q7 Do your guidelines define respect for democracy, human rights, and other users as well as the prohibition of threats of violence as rules every participant needs to respect?

No 0

Yes 1

Part 2.4: Moderation

s2_q8

Does your forum have moderators (at least one moderator)?

Yes 1

No 0

s2_q9

What is the status of these moderators?

Most of them are unpaid volunteers 1

Most of them are part-time employees 2

Most of them are full-time employees 3

s2_q10

How often do your moderators remind users of the existence of guidelines and rules by posting them or sending them to everyone?

Never or up to once a year 0

- More than once a year 1
- At least once a month or every time when the frequency of violations increases 2

s2_q11

Do your moderators try to facilitate discussion by posting summaries, pointing users towards postings or topics made by others?

- No 0
- Yes 1

s2_q12

Does the forum use AI or other technologies for summarising or visualising discussions?

- No 0
- Yes 1

s2_q13

Do the terms of use and guidelines of the discussion forum allow postings that have been created by non-human users (AI, bots, etc.)?

- No, it is explicitly prohibited 1
- Yes, it is explicitly allowed or not prohibited 0

s2_q14

What happens to users who repeatedly violate the forum rules?

- Nothing 0
- They are warned 1
- They are banned or their accounts are deleted 2

Part 2.5: Visibility (colonisation)

s2_q15 Economic colonisation

Does the forum allow users to boost their visibility by paying for it (e.g. by buying advertisements, likes, followers, the increase of visibility and better ranking of comments, etc)?

- No 1
- Yes 0

s2_q16 Political colonisation

Does the forum give increased visibility or usage rights to prominent users or groups (e.g. politicians or celebrities)?

- No 1
- Yes 0

s2_q17 Ideological colonisation

Does the forum propagate a particular worldview that the users are not aware of when

joining or an interest that is not made transparent to the users?

- No 1
- Yes 0

Part 2.6: Activity (Discursive equality)

s2_q18

Can you give an assessment of what share of registered users are highly active participants who regularly participate in online discussions? "Regular" means that they actively post at least one comment to a significant number of topics or have repeatedly opened or brought up new topics themselves.

If you have no data available, please make an informed estimation.

- 0-10%
- 11-20%
- 21-30%
- 31-40%
- 41-50%
- 51-60%
- 61-70%
- 71-80%
- 81-90%
- 91-100%

Coding:

0-20: Low=0

21-40: Medium=1

41-100: High=2

s2_q19

And what share of registered users do you think are so-called "lurkers", users who are registered but never participate actively in discussions by posting comments.

If you have no data available, please make an informed estimation.

- 0-10%
- 11-20%
- 21-30%
- 31-40%
- 41-50%
- 51-60%
- 61-70%
- 71-80%
- 81-90%
- 91-100%

Coding:

41-100%: High=0

21-40%: Medium=1

0-20%: Low=2

Part 2.7: Discussion (quality of discussion)

s2_q20

Can you assess what share of discussed topics resulted in good debates where different views are voiced, arguments tend to be justified, users do not lie, are respectful, reflect on their own and others' comments, talk to and not over and past each other?

If you have no data available, please make an informed estimation.

- 0-10%
- 11-20%
- 21-30%
- 31-40%
- 41-50%
- 51-60%
- 61-70%
- 71-80%
- 81-90%
- 91-100%

Coding:

0-20: Low=0

21-50: Medium=1

51-100: High=2

Part 2.8: Information (truth)

s2_q21

Can you assess how many of 100 postings on average contain false information, misinformation, conspiracy theories, or fake news?

- 0-1
- 2-5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- 21-30
- 31-40
- More than 40

Coding:

0-1: Low=3

2-5: Moderate=1

6-10: High=0

>10: Very High=0

Part 2.9: Insults (rightness, incivility)

s2_q22

Can you assess how many of 100 postings on average contain name-calling and insults (for example other users are characterised as "idiots", "fools", "asshole", "piece of shit", etc.)?

- 0-1
- 2-5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- 21-30
- 31-40
- More than 40

Coding:

0-1: Low=3

2-5: Moderate=2

6-10: High=1

>10: Very High=0

Part 2.10 Threats of violence

s2_q23

Can you assess how many of 1000 postings on average contain threats of violence ("I hope someone beats you up", "I will kill you", "You should be killed", "If I had something to say, you would no longer be around", "This social group should be exterminated", etc.)?

- 0
- 1-2
- 2-5
- 6-10
- 11-20
- More than 20

Coding:

0: Low=3

1-2: Moderate=1

2-5: High=0

>5: Very High=0

Part 2.11: Society (impact on society)

s2_q24

Can you assess how frequently there have been online debates organised by the digital democracy tool that have made an external impact in society by resulting in proposals that are widely debated in the public, changes of rules, laws, or policies, take-up of ideas by political actors (NGOs, parties, politicians, local/regional/transnational government, organisations, etc.)?

- Never 0
- Once 1
- Several times (2-5 times) 2
- More than 5 times 3

3: Participatory Digital Democracy

This section is about e-participation. The tool will ask a series of questions having to do with electronic participation,

Part 3.1: The Participation Process

s3_q1

How many participatory democracy functions does your digital democracy platform/system feature?

- None 0
- One 1
- 2 2
- 3 or more 3

s3_q2

And how many of these participatory democracy functions have been used to try to engage citizens?

- None 0
- Less than 50% of them 1
- 50% or more of them but not all 2
- All of them 3

s3_q3

On average, when digital participatory democracy tools are used for trying to engage citizens, what level of eligible citizens participates?

- 0-1% 0
- 1-5% 1
- 5-15% 2
- More than 15% 3

s3_q4

How accessible are the digital participation tools for citizens with varying digital skills?

Accessibility is here defined as the use of assistive technologies, especially simplified language, sign language, text-to-speech, accessible colours, user-friendliness, more than one language

- There are no accessibility features supporting users with special needs. 0
- There is exactly one assistive feature. 1
- They are two or three assistive features. 2

There are four or more assistive features. 3

s3_q5

What role can citizens play in e-participatory processes via the platform?

They can only submit opinions or complaints. 1

They can contribute or assess ideas for predefined topics (co-ideation, co-assessment, co-evaluation). 2

They can engage in the formulation (co-design, co-creation, co-production, co-delivery) of policies. 3

They become political decision-makers (co-planning and co-commissioning of decisions). 4

They are empowered to engage in the self-management of affairs that concern them and others in the community. 5

s3_q6 The park bench problem:

Digital participation platforms can allow citizens to give input on minor issues (e.g., the colour of park benches, name of the city mascot) or on major decisions (e.g., how a specific share of the community's budget is used, suggestions for city development). What is the role of minor and major issues on your platform?

e-participation only focuses on minor issues 0

e-participation primarily focuses on minor issues 0

e-participation focuses both on minor and major issues to roughly the same degree 1

e-participation primarily focuses on major issues 2

e-participation only focuses on major issues 3

s3_q7

What is the role of online and offline participation?

Participation is possible only online. 0

Participation is possible only offline. 0

Participation is possible both online and offline. 2

s3_q8

Thinking back to the past couple of times e-participation processes were organised, on average, how many offline face-to-face events were organised per e-participation process to promote participation or as part of the participation process?

No offline face-to-face events were organised. 0

One or two offline face-to-face events were organised. 1

Two or more offline face-to-face events were organised. 2

s3_9

In what context is your e-participation tool intended to be used?

It is designed for use in the political system where political decisions are made, political issues are debated, citizens engage in protests, etc. 1

It is designed for use exclusively outside the political system, for example in the workplaces or other economic organisations, or in educational or other cultural organisations. 1

It is flexible and can be used in the political system and other contexts. 3

Part 3.2: Civil Society

Civil society:

The sphere of civil society lies in the public space between the private sphere and the state. Here, citizens organise in groups to pursue their collective interests and ideals. We call these groups civil society organisations (CSOs). CSOs include, but are by no means limited to, interest groups, labour unions, spiritual organisations if they are engaged in civic or political activities, social movements, professional associations, charities, and other non-governmental organisations.

s3_q10

How intensively have civil society organisations taken part in e-participation processes?

- Many civil society organisations have participated many times. 6
- There is a good level of civil society organisation participation. 4
- There is a rather low level of civil society organisation participation. 2
- There is hardly any civil society organisation participation. 1
- There is no civil society organisation participation. 0

s3_q11 In how far does the platform support civil society organisations' and social movements' online activities (several answers are possible)?

- Civil society organisations can use the platform for public announcements. 0/1
- Civil society organisations can use the platform independently as public communication tool. 0/1
- Civil society organisations can use the platform to organise events. 0/1
- Civil society organisations can use the platform to mobilise supporters and volunteers, organise campaigns and initiatives. 0/1
- The platform enables networking and collaboration between different organisations. 0/1
- The platform offers no specific features for civil society organisations. (The platform offers specific features for civil society organisations: 1, The platform offers no specific features for civil society organisations: 0)

Part 3.3: Equal Participation

s3_q12 Class and Poverty

To what degree have measures been taken for trying to increase the importance of people experiencing poverty in e-participation processes conducted via the platform?

We assume that there are three forms of informing and reaching out to citizens: online

information, face-to-face outreach activities (information booths, information events, door knocking), and traditional media use (information letters or brochures, announcements on the radio, on television or in newspapers).

No such measures have been taken. 0

One form of engagement measure has been taken (either online or face-to-face or traditional media). 1

Two forms of engagement measures have been taken. 2

Three/All forms of engagement have been used. 4

s3_q13 Gender:

[Based on V-Dem power distributed by gender (C) (v2pepwrge)]

What is the role of gender, men, and women in e-participation?

Only individuals from one gender participate. 0

Individuals from one gender have a dominant role in e-participation. 0

Individuals from one gender have much more influence in e-participation but individuals from other genders have some influence. 1

Individuals from one gender participate somewhat more than all others. 2

Individuals from all genders engage in e-participation roughly according to their representation in the population. 4

s3_q14 Social Groups:

To what degree have measures been taken for trying to increase the importance of different social groups in e-participation processes conducted via the platform?

Social groups are groups whose roles in society differ in respect to categories such as class, age, ethnicity, caste, language, religion, regional differences (urban/rural), ability/disability.

We assume that there are three forms of informing and reaching out to citizens: online information, face-to-face outreach activities (information booths, information events, door knocking), and traditional media use (information letters or brochures, announcements on the radio, on television or in newspapers).

No such measures have been taken. 0

One form of engagement measure directed at different social groups has been taken (either online or face-to-face or traditional media). 1

Two forms of engagement measures directed at different social groups have been taken. 2

Three/All forms of engagement directed at different social groups have been used. 4

Part 3.4: Resources Supporting e-Participation

s3_q15

An unequal distribution of resources such as wealth, social contacts and influence, time, skills, educational level, can undermine the egalitarian character of democracy so that those with more time, skills, education, wealth, social contacts, influence, etc. participate much more than others and are more effective in their contributions so that they are more heard and have more influence.

Have measures been undertaken to promote the inclusion and empowerment of individuals

and groups who are unlikely to engage in e-participation?

- Yes. 3
- Not yet, but we plan to do so in the future. 0
- No. 0

s3_q16

If yes: How do you assess the intensity of such measures?

- There is a low level of such measures (infrequently). 0
- There is a medium level of such measures (sometimes). 1
- There is a high level of such measures (often). 3

s3_q17

There are citizens who do not have access to the Internet. Have measures been undertaken to try to foster the participation of such citizens?

- No. 0
- Not yet, but we plan to do so in the future. 0
- Yes. 3

s3_q18

If yes, what measures have been undertaken? (multiple answers) max 3

- Local community coaching (e.g. in libraries, educational facilities, community centres), support staff, or training projects for the use of the platform or the Internet in general is offered. 0/1
- We held events targeted at non-Internet users that tried to engage them. 0/1
- It is possible to participate in offline versions for undertaking the actions that the digital technology supports. 0/1

Part 3.5: Human Rights and e-Participation

s3_q19

Does e-participation include mechanisms to review or filter out proposals and contributions that would breach constitutional or human rights standards before they are published or voted on?

- Yes. All proposals are reviewed for compliance with constitutional/human rights norms before being accepted for public discussion or vote. 20
- Somewhat. A review exists but is limited in scope or enforced only in exceptional cases. 10
- No formal review. Proposals are published or voted on regardless of their compatibility with human rights norms. 0
- Unknown or unclear. There is no transparency about review procedures or legal filters. 0

Part 3.6: Effects

s3_q20 Political Uptake

To what extent is input from participatory processes binding or influential in political

decision-making?

It is symbolic and rarely affects decisions. 0

It may be considered but has no clear status. 1

Public administration and representatives must consider and discuss the inputs so that it informs its decisions. 5

Public administration and representatives must turn the results of e-participation processes into formal legislation. 9

Part 3.7: Feedback and Transparency

Does the platform provide transparency about the impact of citizen participation?

No feedback is provided to citizens. 0

Citizens can use an online form, e-mail address, social media, or phone number to contact the authority about the impacts. but no impact summaries or reports are published. 1

Impact summaries or reports are published by the authorities. 2

Citizens can track how their input was used in decision-making. 5

Feedback is given to each contributor. 8

4: Representative Digital Democracy

This section is focused on the electronic support of voting. The tool will ask a series of questions about e-voting.

s4_q1 e-voting system usage:

In what proportion of elections using this system (e.g. at the local or national level) can people vote electronically?

In all of these elections 2

≥ 75 percent of these elections but not all elections 2

≥ 50 and less than 75 percent of these elections 1

≥ 25 and less than 50 percent of these elections 0

More than 0 and less than 25 percent of these elections 0

In none 0

s4_q2 Legal suffrage:

[Based on VDEM Share of population with suffrage (D) (v2x_suffr)]

What share of adult citizens as defined by statute who are living in the community has the legal right to vote in the elections that are conducted with the support of e-voting?

Percentage (as dropdown)

100%: 2

More than 80%: 0

More than 60%: 0

More than 50%: 0

More than 40%: 0

More than 20%: 0

0-20%: 0

s4_q3 Alternative voting options:

Is it possible for those who cannot and do not want to vote electronically to cast their vote in other forms (for example, vote in person and vote by letter)?

Only electronic voting is possible. 0

Yes, there is at least one alternative non-electronic way of casting a vote. 1

Yes, there are at least two alternative non-electronic ways of casting a vote. 2

s4_q4 Misinformation during campaigns:

If there were misinformation and/or fake news campaigns during the election campaign phase that aimed at influencing or manipulating the election results, how did your project/platform react?

There were no reports of misinformation and fake news. 10

There were reports of misinformation and fake news. The project/platform/community did not actively inform citizens about it. 0

There were reports of misinformation and fake news. The project/platform/community informed citizens about it only using online media. 5

There were reports of misinformation and fake news. The project/platform/community informed citizens about it only using offline communication. 5

There were reports of misinformation and fake news. The project/platform/community informed citizens about it using online media and offline communication. 10

s4_q5 Autonomy:

[Based on VDem 3.1.3.3 EMB autonomy v2elembaut]

Does the body managing electronic voting have autonomy from the government to apply election laws and administrative rules impartially?

No. It is controlled by the incumbent government, the military, or another de facto ruling body. 0

Somewhat. It has some autonomy on some issues but on critical issues that influence the outcome of elections, the EMB is partial to the de facto ruling body. 0

Ambiguous. It has some autonomy but is also partial, and it is unclear to what extent this influences the outcome of the election. 2

Almost. It has autonomy and acts impartially almost all the time. It may be influenced by the de facto ruling body in some minor ways that do not influence the outcome of elections. 5

Yes. It is autonomous and impartially applies election laws and administrative rules. 10

s4_q6 Capacity:

[Based on VDem 3.1.3.4 EMB capacity (C) (v2elembcap)]

Does the body managing electronic voting have sufficient staff and resources to administer a well-run electronic vote?

No. There are glaring deficits in staff, financial, or other resources affecting the

organisation across the territory. 0

Not really. Deficits are not glaring but they nonetheless seriously compromised the organisation of administratively well-run e-voting processes in many parts of the country. 0

Ambiguous. There might be serious deficiencies compromising the organisation of the election but it could also be a product of human errors and coincidence or other factors outside the control of the organisation. 0

Mostly. There are partial deficits in resources but these are neither serious nor widespread. 1

Yes. The organisation has adequate staff and other resources to administer a well-run e-voting process. 2

s4q_7 Internal interference in digital elections:

To what extent do you believe recent electronic elections were fair and free from internal manipulation and technical irregularities by the council/city/project/platform organising the election (e.g., vote buying via digital transfers, coercion through surveillance or app control, digital voter intimidation through threats such as threats of violence, harassment and intimidation etc.)?

Completely free – no credible signs of manipulation 10

Mostly free – minor concerns, but generally fair 4

Somewhat manipulated – noticeable irregularities or coercion 0

Heavily manipulated – major integrity issues observed 0

Completely unfree – widespread digital manipulation 0

s4_q8 Foreign or external interference in digital elections:

To what extent do you believe recent electronic elections were targeted or influenced by external forces such as political parties, foreign actors, local or national interest groups (e.g., foreign disinformation campaigns involving fake news, deep fakes, etc., coordinated social media manipulation, cyberattacks on election infrastructure, or other forms of foreign information manipulation and interference)?

No evidence – no signs of foreign interference 10

Low – limited attempts, with minimal effect 4

Moderate – visible efforts, unclear outcome 0

High – foreign interference significantly affected the election 0

Extreme – election integrity severely compromised by external actors 0

s4_q9 e-Voter registry accuracy:

[Based on V-DEM 3.1.3.6 Election voter registry (C) (v2elrgstry)]

In e-voting processes, was there a reasonably accurate voter registry in place, and was it used?

No. There was no registry, or the registry was not used. 0

No. There was a registry but it was fundamentally flawed (meaning 20% or more of eligible voters could have been disenfranchised or the outcome could have been affected

significantly by double-voting and impersonation). 0

Uncertain. There was a registry but it is unclear whether potential flaws in the registry had much impact on electoral outcomes. 0

Yes, somewhat. The registry was imperfect but less than 5% of eligible voters may have been disenfranchised, and double-voting and impersonation could not have affected the results significantly. 4

Yes. The voter registry was reasonably accurate (less than 1% of voters were affected by any flaws) and it was applied in a reasonable fashion. 10

s4_q10 Accessibility & usability:

To what extent is the e-voting system accessible and usable for all eligible voters, including those with disabilities or low digital skills?

Answer Options:

Not at all. There are significant barriers for many voter groups. 0

Slightly. Some support features exist, but key groups face difficulties. 0

Moderately. Basic accessibility and usability measures are in place. 1

Very. Most voters can use the system easily and independently. 1

Completely. Fully accessible and usable by all voter groups, including those with disabilities and low digital literacy. 2

s4_q11 e-voting eligibility:

e-voting eligibility means that only eligible voters can vote and that each eligible voter can only vote once (one-person-one-vote principle). How effective are the measures that your e-voting platform uses to ensure voter eligibility?

Not at all effective. No reliable eligibility checks are in place (high risk of ineligible or multiple votes). 0

Slightly effective. Minimal measures (basic identity checks with limited protection against duplicate voting). 2

Effective. Standard verification processes exist (eligible voters are verified and duplicate-vote prevention is in place). 6

Very effective – Strong measures implemented (robust voter authentication and clear one-vote-per-voter enforcement following best practices). 8

Extremely effective – Comprehensive, state-of-the-art measures fully ensure that only eligible individuals vote and each person votes only once, aligning with recognised best practices for election integrity. 10

s4_q12 e-voting security:

e-voting security involves three key elements:

Integrity – ensuring that votes cannot be changed, deleted, or tampered with after being cast.

Authenticity – ensuring that only eligible and verified users are allowed to vote.

Availability – ensuring that the platform remains accessible and functional during the voting period

How confident are you in the platform's overall security across these three areas?

- Not confident at all. I do not trust the platform's security. 0
- Somewhat unconfident. I have concerns about one or more of these areas. 1
- Neutral. I'm unsure how secure the platform is. 3
- Somewhat confident. I trust most aspects, but have minor concerns. 5
- Very confident. I trust the platform's security on all three aspects. 8

s4_q13: Privacy

Privacy in e-voting means protecting the anonymity of each voter's choice and preventing any possibility of coercion. This ensures voters can express their will freely without fear of retribution or pressure.

To what extent does your e-voting platform protect voter privacy — by ensuring vote anonymity and preventing coercion or vote tracing?

- Not at all. Votes can be linked to individuals; risk of coercion is high. 0
- Slightly. Some anonymisation is used, but voter identity might still be inferred. 0
- Basic protections exist; vulnerabilities cannot be fully ruled out. 1
- Completely. There are strong anonymity measures, voter choices are fully anonymised and untraceable by any party. 2

s4_q14: Verifiability & transparency

Verifiability and transparency refer to the ability of voters and observers to confirm that votes are recorded and counted correctly, without compromising voters' privacy. These properties are critical for building public trust and ensuring the legitimacy of election results.

How well does your e-voting platform support verifiability and transparency? How well does it allow voters and independent observers to verify that votes are correctly recorded and counted?

- Not at all. No mechanisms for verification or public transparency. 0
- Slightly. Limited technical logs or reports available; not independently verifiable. 0
- Moderately. Voters or officials can check some parts of the process. 2
- Very well. End-to-end verifiability is supported with clear audit trails. 4
- Completely. Full voter and observer verifiability implemented, with publicly inspectable evidence and no compromise to privacy. 8

s4_q15: Post-election auditability

How well does your e-voting platform support independent, post-election audits — including the ability to trace, reconstruct, and legally defend the election outcome?

- Not at all. No logs or audit trails exist, or they are inaccessible or unreliable. 0
- Slightly. Some audit data is available but lacks integrity or legal standing. 0
- Moderately. Audit trails exist and can be reviewed internally but lack full transparency or legal rigour. 2
- Very well. The system supports tamper-evident logs and auditability by designated authorities. 4
- Completely. The system provides secure, comprehensive, and independently verifiable audit trails suitable for legal and public scrutiny. 8

s4_q16: Incident response & recovery

In the event of a technical failure, cyberattack, or dispute over election results, how effective are your system's response procedures for managing incidents and restoring election integrity?

- Not effective. There are no defined or tested procedures for incident response or recovery. 0
- Slightly effective. Informal or ad hoc processes exist but lack coordination or reliability. 0
- Moderately effective. There are formal plans, but they haven't been tested or may not cover all failure scenarios. 1
- Very effective. Incident response and recovery procedures exist, are documented, and have been tested or used. 2
- Extremely effective. The system includes robust, regularly tested incident response protocols and full recovery capabilities with minimal disruption to election integrity. 2

s4_q17 Scalability & sustainability

Definition: Scalability and sustainability refer to an e-voting system and platform's capacity to handle large-scale elections and adapt over time to technological changes. A robust e-voting system and platform should perform reliably under load, evolve with security standards, and remain maintainable long-term.

How capable is your e-voting system and platform in terms of scalability and sustainability, how reliably does it operate under high demand, and how usable and secure does it remain over time?

- Not capable. The system and platform cannot handle large electorates or evolving tech requirements. 0
- Somewhat capable. It is suitable for small-scale use, with limited flexibility. 0
- Moderately capable. It manages current demands, but may struggle with future growth. 1
- Highly capable. It is designed to scale and adapt with reasonable upgrades. 2
- Fully capable. It has the proven ability to scale for large elections with many voters and can adapt long-term with minimal disruption. 2

5: Direct Digital Democracy

This section is focused on direct democracy. The tool will ask a couple of questions about this topic.

Part 5.1: Direct Digital Democracy Mechanisms

s5_q1 Legal provision

[Based on V-DEM v2ddlexci, v2ddlexrf, v2ddlexpl, v2ddlexci]

What is the legal provision for conducting direct democratic mechanisms such as citizens' initiatives, referenda, or plebiscites electronically?

- Such mechanisms are legally allowed but are non-binding and have an advisory function (or there is an intervening institutional veto). 4

Such mechanisms are allowed and binding. 7

s5_q2 Citizen signature threshold (quorum):

What share of eligible voters needs to have cast their digital ballot in order for the initiative to be considered legally valid?

0%-5% 0

>5%-10% 2

>10%-15% 4

>15%-25% 8

> 25%-51% 4

> 51% 0

s5_q3 Vote approval threshold

[Based on V-DEM v2ddspmci, v2ddspmrf, v2ddspmor, v2ddspmpl]

What percentage (%) of the vote is regarded as sufficient, by law, for the approval or success of the digital direct democratic vote in the case of matters that do not concern the national constitution?

>50%-51%

>51%-60%

>60-66.6%

≤50% or >66.6%

Coding:

>50%-51%: very good=8

>51%-60%: good=6

>60-66.6%: poor=3

≤ 50% or >66.6%: very poor=0

s5_q4: Credibility of results

If direct democratic electronic elections occurred in the last five years, what share of them was credible?

Clarification: "Credible" means whether the official results of the vote(s) reflect the actual vote. In the context of e-voting, credibility includes technical security measures that secure the system against manipulation and fraud, secrecy of the online ballot (ballot count should not be conducted in real time and should not be transmitted over the Internet in real time as this can influence the independence of voters' decisions), incorrect vote counting (either due to technical issues or conscious manipulation), etc.

None of the elections were credible. 0

Less than half were credible. 1

Not all, but more than half were credible. 2

All were credible. 7

Part 5.2: Constitutionalism of Direct Digital Democracy Mechanisms

s5_q5: Constitutional boundaries for direct votes

Are there legal or constitutional safeguards that prevent direct e-votes (e.g., referenda or plebiscites initiated by law or government or citizens) from violating fundamental human rights?

- Yes: The legal or constitutional framework explicitly prohibits initiatives, plebiscites or referenda that violate constitutional rights, human rights, or minority protections. 20
- Yes: Legal mechanisms exist, and such proposals are usually blocked by courts or oversight bodies, though not always preemptively. 15
- Partially: There are general protections, but they may be inconsistently enforced or easily bypassed. 2
- No: The system allows binding direct votes even if they may violate human rights or constitutional guarantees. 0

s5_q6: Integration of rights-based review in digital democracy tools

Does the digital direct democracy system include mechanisms to review or filter out proposals that would breach constitutional or human rights standards before they reach a vote or platform?

- Yes. All proposals are reviewed for compliance with constitutional/human rights norms before being accepted for public discussion or vote. 15
- Somewhat. A review exists but is limited in scope or enforced only in exceptional cases. 5
- No formal review. Proposals are published or voted on regardless of their compatibility with human rights norms. 0
- Unknown or unclear. There is no transparency about review procedures or legal filters. 0

6: Pluralist Digital Democracy

Section 6 is based on the mode of decision-making. The tool will ask some questions about it.

Part 6.1: Voice (pluralism of voice)

s6_q1

Does the information on the platform (content, discussions, proposals, etc.) represent a wide range of democratic political perspectives?

- There is mainly one perspective represented. 0
- There is only one perspective represented and an alternative perspective that is approved by the representatives of the first perspective. 0
- There is a variety of democratic political perspectives but at least one democratic political perspective that is important in this society is systematically ignored. 0
- All democratic perspectives that are important in this society are represented. 3

s6_q2

To what extent does such information reflect minority groups' positions?

- Positions of minorities are never mentioned. 0

- Positions of minorities are sometimes mentioned. 1
- Positions of minorities are discussed a great deal. 2

Part 6.2: Echo chambers

s6_q3

An echo chamber is a relatively closed space of information and communication where only one political position is represented and other voices are excluded.

On the platform in question, to what extent would you say are there online echo chambers, either with respect to the platform as a whole or certain features such as discussion forums?

- Echo chambers play no role on the platform. 3
- Echo chambers play a very small role on the platform 2
- Echo chambers play some role on the platform. 1
- Echo chambers play an important role on the platform. 0
- Echo chambers predominate the platform. 0

Part 6.3: Online activity

s6_q4

When users are asked to undertake some activity on the platform (for example, respond to something, post something, debate, draft something, or any other form of information production or participation), what share of registered users typically participate at least once?

- 0-1 out of 100 users 0
- 2-5 out of 100 users 0
- 6-10 out of 100 users 0
- 11-15 out of 100 users 1
- 16-20 out of 100 users 1
- 21-30 out of 100 users 1
- 31-40 out of 100 users 2
- More than 40 out of 100 users 3

s6_q5

When users are asked to undertake some activity on the platform (for example, respond to something, post something, debate, draft something, information production or participation), on average, what share of users engages continuously by posting something several times, engaging in discussions several times, etc.?

- 0-1 out of 100 users 0
- 2-5 out of 100 users 1
- 6-10 out of 100 users 2
- 11-15 out of 100 users 3
- 16-20 out of 100 users 3
- 21-30 out of 100 users 3
- 31-40 out of 100 users 3

- More than 40 out of 100 users 3
- More than 40 out of 100 users 3

Part 6.4: Polarisation

s6_q6

How would you characterise the differences of opinions on political issues on this platform? While plurality of views exists in all societies, we are interested in knowing the extent to which these differences in opinions result in major clashes of views and polarisation.

- Serious polarisation. There are serious differences in opinions on the platform on almost all key political issues, which result in major clashes of views, including frequent hate speech or even threats of violence. 0
- Polarisation: There are significant differences in opinions on the platform that result in significant clashes of views that include insults and defamation. 0
- Moderate polarisation. There are differences in opinions on the platform on key political issues, which result in moderate clashes of views, including the use of swearwords. 1
- Limited polarisation. Differences in opinions in a few cases result in clashes of views involving heated debates. 2
- Little polarisation. There are differences in opinions, but these differences are by and large expressed in a civil and constructive manner. 3

Part 6.5: Minorities

s6_q7

When there are decisions taken by the participants via the platform that result in new policies, projects, or other changes: According to official policy, how often should the will of the majority expressed on the platform (for example by voting) be implemented even if the resulting policy or action would violate the human or civil rights of minorities?

- Always. It is official policy that the will of the majority should always be implemented even if the resulting policy violates the human or civil rights of minorities. 0
- Usually. It is official policy that the will of the majority should usually be implemented even if the resulting policy violates the human or civil rights of minorities. 0
- Half of the time. It is official policy that the will of the majority should about half of the time be implemented even if the resulting policy violates the human or civil rights of minorities. 0
- Usually not. It is official policy that the will of the majority should usually not be implemented if the resulting policy violates the human or civil rights of minorities. 1
- Never. It is official policy that the will of the majority should never be implemented if the resulting policy violates the human or civil rights of minorities. 3

Feedback on the Digital Democracy Score (DDS)

We appreciate if you can provide feedback on the Digital Democracy Score (DDS), which will just take 30 seconds.

Thank you!

How helpful did you find the Digital Democracy Score (DDS) tool?

Very Good 4

Good 3

Medium 2

Sufficient 1

Poor 0

How easy or difficult to use did you find the tool?

Very easy to use 4

Easy to use 3

Medium level 2

Difficult to use 1

Very difficult to use 0

Do you have comments about the Digital Democracy Score (DDS) tool that you want to make?